

Shock Index and Lactate Level as Prognostic Factors of 24-Hour Mortality in Polytraumatized Patients in Emergency Services

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INTRODUCTION

Trauma is third in the world in terms of causes of mortality, accounting for 10% of all deaths. It is the primary cause of mortality for most persons under 40 and leads to severe disabilities. In addition, an increasing proportion of senior trauma patients are at increased risk of mortality. Hemorrhage is one of the two main causes of mortality after trauma, with 80% of deaths occurring within 48 hours. As a result, early, individualized treatment and proper triage are critical components of the trauma system, matching resources to the severity of the patient's injuries without overburdening the system. Whether to send a patient to a trauma center is the first choice made during triage¹⁻⁴.

Metabolic parameters, such as initial serum lactate and its variation, are very accurate markers of blood loss and may be used as prognostic indicators in trauma patients. Traditional vital signs, which measure tissue perfusion, are specific but not highly sensitive indicators of hemorrhage. Therefore, in trauma patients with normal vital signs, serum lactate may be useful in differentiating between mild and serious injuries. Therefore, the goal of early trauma management is not only to diagnose and treat the effects of trauma, but also to identify the factors that are likely to indicate that this early therapy will be successful⁵⁻⁷.

While there are many factors to consider while managing trauma patients, identifying and controlling bleeding is the

most crucial one. The most important factor influencing a patient's prognosis after trauma and the leading cause of mortality is massive bleeding. Stated differently, halting bleeding is the most crucial action that might enhance the patient's prognosis and lower the chance of death during the fabled "golden hour." Furthermore, the cornerstones of trauma patient care are early diagnosis and management of bleeding. Reducing the symptoms of shock is a persistent challenge for these individuals. Hypoperfusion and shock increase the risk of inadequate oxygen supply, coagulopathy, infection, organ failure, tissue hypoxia, anaerobic metabolism, lactate production, and, eventually, late hospital mortality^{8,9}.

Trauma patients who have suffered severe injuries have been reported to have inadequate tissue oxygenation in up to 85% of cases, even after meeting the standard resuscitation criteria of normal systolic and diastolic pressure, cardiac frequency, and urine output. Because of this, it's recommended to stratify patients based on whether they require ongoing fluid resuscitation and to utilize serum lactate measurements as a signal to identify individuals who require early, aggressive resuscitation¹⁰.

Controlling bleeding, however, is not an easy task. On-site compression can be used to control definitive external bleeding caused by trauma. However, for a variety of reasons, internal bleeding resulting from internal organ damage and

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large proximal bone fractures in the pelvis is frequently undetected, delaying treatment. Trauma patients may develop coagulopathy or systemic acidosis if they fail to administer hemorrhage control at the appropriate time. Furthermore, death is the result of this deadly trio^{11,12}.

It was predicted that hospital death rates would rise significantly in patients whose lactate did not return to normal during the first twenty-four hours¹³.

Usefulness of shock index

The value of SI in polytrauma patients' bleeding diagnosis was emphasized¹⁴.

An rise in delta SI denotes hypovolemic shock, persistent bleeding, and inadequate resuscitation during transport. Delta SI represents the change in trauma severity. Only by monitoring vital signs without the need for extra equipment can Delta SI be computed, which is useful for making clinical decisions for patients who have had acute stage trauma¹⁵.

In a trauma scenario, patients who are elderly, on β -blockers, or pregnant do not bleed according to the typical physiology and exhibit distinct alterations in vital signs. When we analyze patients with conflicting circumstances, delta SI has a better sensitivity than the single cross-sectional SI since it is generated using changes obtained at two sites. Furthermore, when trauma happens, individuals who have these perplexing characteristics are typically more likely to die. As a result, delta SI helps patients who have experienced high-risk trauma survive. Additionally, triage, objective severity evaluation, and communication of patient severity information between the trauma site and ED are benefits of delta SI. Therefore, in patients with trauma-related hypovolemic shock, delta SI may be useful in predicting mortality and informing treatment decisions during the early acute phase of the condition¹⁶.

Blood lactate

In 2015, Dezman and associates demonstrated that the inability to completely remove serum lactate following an injury was a consistent predictor of a dismal outcome. In fact, compared to patients whose serum lactate levels returned to normal, the 24-hour hospital mortality rate was almost seven times greater. The prognosis of trauma patients in the current study was linked to non-normalization of serum lactate during the first 24 hours, although this association did not serve as a risk factor for hospital death. This may be because we opted to include patients who had normal blood lactate levels upon admission to our study, which may have resulted in a cohort that was too diverse to draw any firm conclusions¹⁷.

Nevertheless, serum lactate clearance is probably insufficient to identify concealed hypo-perfusion, even if it can be useful in assessing the early resuscitation provided to trauma patients¹⁸.

CONCLUSION

Additionally useful markers of a patient's state of shock include lactate and BE, although obtaining results after

arriving at the hospital takes around an hour. It was also shown that scoring systems, such ISS and TRISS, had a strong correlation with the prognosis of trauma patients. Nevertheless, because these ratings represent the last outcomes following all workups, there is limited opportunity for early detection. A computed tomography (CT) scan can clearly demonstrate bleeding. Nevertheless, depending on the patient's state, CT might be challenging to do, and the advanced trauma life support guideline advises against doing so during the main surveillance phase.

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